

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION 1

Ship ahoy! Prayers on the walls: votive offerings and engravings on the island of Oléron in France.

¡Barco a la vista! Oraciones en las paredes: ofrendas votivas y grabados en la isla de Oléron, Francia.

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The following files contain images of the most identifiable engravings found in churches on the island of Oléron. Below is a map showing which churches house the engravings. The files contain the following information:

1. Name of the church
2. Location of the church on the map
3. Coordinates
4. Location of the graffiti on the photo of the church floor plan
5. Photograph of the engraving and representation of the same
6. What material is the graffiti made of?
7. What material is it believed to have been made with?
8. Proposed typology
9. Proposed chronology
10. Description: when it is not a ship

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Location of the island of Oléron: <https://maps.app.goo.gl/5Ld2ftcp5oJoyKVG9>

<p>SAINT GEORGES D'OLÉRON</p> <p>Coordinates:</p> <p>X: 629255</p> <p>Y: 5093090</p>	
<p>The floor plan of the church and the room where the graffiti was found are shown here:</p>	
<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the central nave, right by the entrance to the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SGO1</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Cog or merchant ship (<i>nao</i>)</p> <p>Possible chronology: Medieval</p>	

<p>SAINT PIERRE D'OLÉRON</p> <p>Coordinates:</p> <p>X: 631263</p> <p>Y: 5089276</p>	
<p>The floor plan of the church and the room where the graffiti was found are shown here:</p>	
<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the narthex, which is located under the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO1</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: three-masted ship; fly-boat, carrack or galleon</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 17th or 18th centuries</p>	

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<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the narthex, which is located under the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO2-1 (black) and SPO2-2 (blue)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Black: line-of-battle ship; Blue: brigantine.</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 18th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the narthex, which is located under the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO3</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Schooner</p> <p>Possible chronology: 18th to 20th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO4</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: line-of-battle ship or frigate</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife and blunt object</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO5-1 (black), SPO5-2 (green), SPO5-3 (red)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Black: line-of-battle ship or frigate; Green: ¿corvette?; Red: xebec</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Charcoal</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO6</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: brigantine-schooner or barquentine</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 19th century</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO7-1 (black) and SPO7-2 (red)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Black: single-sailed boat, <i>filandière?</i>; Red: heavy-lift vessel</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the narthex, which is located under the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife and charcoal</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SPO8 (entire panel)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Possible harbour scene</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

<p>SAINT ANDRÉ DE DOLUS</p> <p>Coordinates:</p> <p>X: 634676</p> <p>Y: 5085632</p>	
<p>The floor plan of the church and the room where the graffiti was found are shown here:</p>	
<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created in the narthex, which is located under the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD1</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: single-masted sailing ship</p> <p>Possible chronology: ?</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD2</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: ¿Corvette? ¿Frigate?</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD3-1 (black) and SAD3-2 (blue)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Fly-boat (black).</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 18th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD4</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Brick-barque</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 17th to 18th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD5-1 (black), SAD5-2 (blue), SAD5-3 (green)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Sketches of three-masted ships</p> <p>Possible chronology: 17th to 18th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD6</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: three-masted ship</p> <p>Possible chronology: 16th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD7</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: three-masted ship</p> <p>Possible chronology: 16th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD8</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Sketch of a ship and other lines</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: ?</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD 9 (entire panel) and SAD9-1 (red)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Possible harbour scene</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD9-1</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: <i>couraux</i> and <i>coraline</i></p> <p>Possible chronology: 18th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p>Engraving and photography: SAD10</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: three-masted ship; ¿galleon? ¿line-of-battle ship?</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 16th to 19th centuries</p>	

<p style="text-align: center;">NOTRE-DAME DE L'ASSOMPTION DE LE CHÂTEAU</p> <p>Coordinates:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">X: 639915</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Y: 5083250</p>	
<p>The floor plan of the church and the room where the graffiti was found are shown here:</p>	
<p>Location description: The engraving or graffiti was created on the staircase that leads up to the bell tower.</p>	
<p>The material on which the graffiti was made: Limestone ashlar</p>	
<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Engraving and photography: NDA1</p>	
<p>Summary of main features: An anthropomorphic figure can be seen sitting with his legs open on a log or barrel. One of his legs appears to be a wooden leg. They are attempting to create a side view, as if looking at the figure from the side, so they depict the arms in a forced pose. Both arms reach towards an instrument, surrounding it. It appears that the musician is forcing his mouth open to insert a mouthpiece. Initially, it looked as if he was raising one arm with something in his hand, but both arms can now be seen reaching towards the instrument, with the fingers surrounding it. Therefore, we believe that he is playing the bagpipes, and that the object protruding behind him is the drone. The bell is represented as a square shape with a line through it. We do not know whether this is the bell or an image of a flag. If so, we might be looking at the bagpipe of a Scottish sailor who decorated it with an image of his country's flag instead of tassels. This practice was already in use in the modern period.</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Engraving and photography: NDA2</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: Brick-barque Possible chronology: 17th to 18th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Engraving and photography: NDA3</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: three-masted ship; ¿corvette? ¿frigate?</p>	
<p>Possible chronology: 17th to 19th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Engraving and photography: NDA4-1 (black) and NDA4-2 (green)</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: ketch and cutter. Possible chronology: 18th to 20th centuries</p>	

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<p>Material used to create the graffiti: Knife</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Engraving and photography: NDA5</p>	
<p>Proposed typology: galleon</p> <p>Possible chronology: 16th century</p>	